

X, Time Degeneracy in Nonrelativistic and Relativistic Mechanics

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The objective of nonrelativistic mechanics is to obtain $x(t)$ which does not seem to have anything to do with x , time degeneracy. The idea of degeneracy, however, directly appears when one considers a constant velocity and argues that $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is length. This probability equation suggests that each x point carries the same weight or is degenerate with respect to probability. In other words, there is infinite x resolution. A similar argument holds for time.

Constant speed in special relativity should represent a similar thing, i.e. $x=vt$ (or $x-p/E t=0$) and $P(x)dx = dx/L$. L is an arbitrary length. Thus, one might at first suggest infinite x and t resolution. This in fact follows as a solution of the Lorentz invariant $0 = -Edt + p dx$. (independent of $x-vt=0$). Given that this equation has nothing to do with a trajectory, it may be rejected as unphysical, but we suggest that this equation has the solution $dx=dt=0$, demonstrating x and t resolution.

There is, however, a second math solution, namely $dt = \text{constant}/E$ and $dx = \text{constant}/p$. This solution forces an x and t resolution which is non-infinite. Thus, one must choose between the two solutions and we argue that an infinite x and t resolution is not physical. This leads to a dramatic consequence that an E and p (constant) actually define time and spatial gradations, an idea which is used in quantum mechanics.

Nonrelativistic Mechanics

Nonrelativistic mechanics seeks to find $x(t)$, i.e. $x=vt$ for a constant v . In an interval in x and t , one may choose each x and t with the same probability weight such that $x=vt$. Thus, there seems to be infinite x and t resolution and all x points are degenerate as are all t points as long as $x=vt$. Another way to view this is to state that if one breaks the x axis into equally spaced dx units, then the same dt is associated with each. Alternatively, one may consider:

$P(x)dx = dx/L$ where $L = \text{length}$ and note that this is a uniform distribution ((1))

Special Relativity

In special relativity, for a given frame one again has $x=vt$. In another frame, $x' = v' t'$, but the form of the equation is the same and the x and t values have the same degeneracy and there is always the same infinite x and t resolution.

One may write:

$$X' - v't' = 0 \quad ((2))$$

In special relativity, however, there is a second equation which may be written in the form of ((2)), namely:

$$A \text{ invariant} = -Et + px = 0 \quad ((3))$$

We note first that ((3)) is incompatible with ((2)). In other words, x, t points which satisfy ((2)) are associated with a trajectory whereas in ((3)) they are not. As a result, why does one consider ((3)) at all? The trajectory is the physical path in the problem of a constant p whereas ((3)) is only a mathematical consideration.

We argue that ((3)) is more than a mathematical consideration. If one writes:

$$0 = -E dt + p dx \quad ((5))$$

then $dt=0$ and $dx=0$ is a solution which matches the nonrelativistic idea that one has infinite resolution in x and t and that all x and t points have the same weight. Thus, ((3)) is not simply a math result, but one that is concerned with resolution.

We note that there is a second solution to ((3)) namely:

$$dt = \text{constant}/E \text{ and } dx = \text{constant}/p \quad ((6))$$

At first, one may ask what one should correlate dx and dt if they have nothing to do with the actual motion of the particle which is governed by ((2)). We suggest that ((5)) represents the creation of resolution in x and t . A dx is laid down in dt , then a second dx in another dt etc. The resolution in x and t is a completely different thing from the trajectory and physical motion in x and t .

The consequences of ((6)) are important because it suggests noninfinite x and t resolution which seems to be physical while the $dt = dx = 0$ infinite resolution is not.

The reason why ((5)) arises in special relativity is that it represents an independent equation relating E, p and x, t . $x=vt$ may be written as:

$$x - p/E t = 0 \quad (c=1) \quad ((7)), \text{ but this is not the same as } ((5)) \text{ i.e. } px - Et = 0$$

Thus, there must be some important x, t information associated with ((5)) which is not captured in ((7)). In general, it seems that given the focus on the trajectory $x(t)$, i.e. $x=vt$, for both special relativity and nonrelativistic mechanics, that the x, t relationship in $A=px-Et$ is not considered.

We suggest that even though it has nothing to do with the trajectory, it does seem to be linked to finite resolution of x and t which appears in quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

Classical mechanics, whether it be nonrelativistic or relativistic, seems to focus on the particle trajectory $x(t)$. For a particle with constant v , this means that $x=vt$ and that one has

infinite x and t resolution. This holds in both nonrelativistic mechanics and special relativity and may be written as: $x - p/E t = 0$ where $p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv}$ and $E = mo/\sqrt{1-vv}$ $c=1$.

The problem is that there exists a second x, t, E, p equation in special relativity which is independent of $x - p/E t = 0$, namely: $A = -Et + px$. If one chooses $A=0$, then one has x, t pairs which have nothing to do with the trajectory, which may be why this equation is ignored. We suggest, however, that writing $0 = -E dt + p dx$ leads to the usual $dt = dx = 0$ infinite resolution solution as well as a $dt = \text{constant}/E$, $dx = \text{constant}/p$ solution. We suggest that infinite resolution is unphysical and choose the latter, which is the quantum mechanical approach. We suggest that dt and dx are coupled in $0 = -E dt + p dx$ because one is creating dx in dt , then the next dx gradation in the next dt etc.